

A Study on Buying Behaviour of Women towards Selected Fast Moving Consumer Goods at Palayamkottai” - with special reference on Influencing Factors

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Abstract

The Fast Moving Consumer Goods sector (FMCG) makes a decisive contribution to India's GDP growth. Fast Moving Consumer products are not a single product. It is a generic term that includes many different products. This includes cosmetics and toiletries, personal care products, fabric cleaners, household cleaners, food products, etc. Therefore, it is necessary to identify changes in consumers' buying behaviour with respect to Fast Moving Consumer products. The purpose of this Paper is to identify the factors that influence consumers' purchasing behaviour with respect to FMCG products and finally make decisions. The data of this study were collected through a questionnaire and the results were presented in an analytical table. Find the reason among the factors that influence the selected FMCGs products. This study is as significant as the current evolution in the retail sector. The results will help to design appropriate strategies for selling Fast Moving Consumer Products to customers.

Key Word: Buying Behaviour of Women, Fast Moving Consumer Goods, Selected FMCG Product, Influencing Factors.

INTRODUCTION

The rapidly evolving Fast Moving Consumer Goods sector touches every aspect of human life. This sector is an important part of the consumer's budget in all countries. The rapidly growing consumer goods sector in India has begun to take shape over the last fifty

years. The sector is enthusiastic about the growth of the rural population whose incomes are increasing and who are willing to spend on the purchase of goods intended to improve the way of life. Faced with near-saturation and intense competition in urban India, many fast-moving consumer goods producers have come up with new bold strategies to target rural consumers in a targeted way. This represents a great opportunity for retailers of branded products, which can convert consumers into branded products. Many companies, including multinationals and regional players, have begun to develop marketing strategies to attract the untapped market. The benefits of fast moving consumer goods are relatively minimal and sales are huge, which has generated significant profits for these products. Consumer goods companies face intense competition and are forced to find new ways to make money. However, this is very difficult because consumers have different needs, different expectations and a drastic change in living standards and lifestyles.

Fast Moving Consumer Goods

Fast moving consumer goods are goods consumed daily by the average consumer that are replaced or fully used in a short period of days, weeks or months and within a year. Fast Moving Consumer goods (FMCG) are commonly referred to as "packaged consumer goods". Items in this category include all consumables, people buy at regular intervals. The most common personal care products are shampoos, hair oils, bath soaps, toothpaste, cosmetics, etc. These items are intended for frequent daily consumption.

Women Buying Behaviour

Women in today's market cannot be considered a homogeneous group. Their diversity in terms of psychosocial status must be accepted and taken into account by marketers in segmenting a market. There are differences in women's consumption patterns, purchase patterns, priorities and response to advertising. Marketers and advertisers are increasingly aware of the greater role of women in decision-making, in particular for fast moving consumer goods and services. A market research report indicates that women remain the main users of goods in the cosmetics and toiletry sector, with around eight out of ten women claiming to buy most of the cosmetics and toiletries in their homes.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Women are involved in purchasing decisions in most product categories, women's involvement in most purchasing decisions has been absent until recently. The woman does not intervene in the decision to buy consumer goods, even quickly, in the first few days. Now

the trend has changed and women are making purchasing decisions, particularly for rapidly changing consumer goods brands. Although consumers are more dynamic, their tastes and preferences also change; women find various influential factors in choosing their fast moving consumer goods.

Objectives

The main objective of the present work is to study:

- To know the influencing factors of women to purchase fast moving consumer goods.
- To find out the brand preference of women towards selected FMCG product.
- To examine decision to purchase women towards FMCG product.

Review of Literature

Bhawna Garg (2007) studied consumer behaviour towards hair oil in rural areas and highlighted the factors that influence it. Brand selection, purchase frequency, brand preferences, loyalty, etc. have emerged as useful aspects of behavioural study. The study concluded that television advertising has a significant impact on hair oil consumers. The perfume factor dominated the purchase of hair oils.

Vaishnani (2012) examined the perception of brand equity by referring to sales promotion programs for selected consumer goods. The results revealed that there was no significant difference between the gender perception of brand equity as one of the demographic variables. Apart from that, it was concluded that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the value of a brand among the various occupational states. Furthermore, it is clear that independent consumers perceive sales promotion systems less favourably.

Thanigachalam (2014) In his article, he emphasizes "consumer behaviour towards rapidly evolving FMCG goods in Pondicherry". The importance of promotional offers, the availability of brands is important so that companies pay sufficient attention before planning and implementing their marketing strategies. The sector of essential goods is a very dynamic sector in India. An important goal is to meet the needs and desires of consumers and their target markets more efficiently and effectively.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, an analytical method of influencing factors of selected FMCG products was used.

SAMPLE

The sample size consists of 82 women consumers and the respondents were selected from convenient method based. The area of the study is Palayamkottai. It is known as “Oxford of South India”, is a town in the Tirunelveli district of Tamilnadu.

DATA FOR THE STUDY

The primary data were collected from questionnaire through 82 respondents and the secondary data were collected from internet, journals, books, articles etc.,

Statistical Tools

Appropriate statistical tools like simple Percentage analysis, Mean and F - test were applied with the help of SPSS software version 19.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following table shows brief analysis of influencing factors of selected FMCG products was used.

H₀ : There is no Significant Relation between various type of Age group with regard to Influencing Factors of selected FMCG products

I. No.	Particulars	Age group			Total	F-Test Value	P-Value
		Below 20 years	20 – 40 years	Above 40 years			
Shampoo							
1	The Shampoo Makes Hair Dry	3.47	3.63	4.10	3.68	2.567	.083
2	The Shampoo Cause Hair Fall	3.53	3.44	3.60	3.51	.171	.843
3	The Shampoo Cleans Scalp and Hair Dandruff	3.20	3.31	4.00	3.44	3.376	.039*
Bath Soap							
1	The Soap Makes Skin Soft	3.73	3.56	3.60	3.63	.350	.706
2	The Soap has Fragrance	3.53	3.50	4.10	3.66	3.568	.033*
3	The Soap gives good complexion/ colour of Skin	3.60	2.63	3.10	3.10	5.785	.005**
Tooth Paste							
1	The Toothpaste Gives Freshness	3.93	3.94	4.20	4.00	.974	.382
2	The Toothpaste Makes Teeth Strong	3.80	3.50	3.50	3.61	1.358	.263
3	The Toothpaste Whiten your Teeth	3.67	3.56	3.60	3.61	.106	.899
Hair Oil							
1	The Hair Oil Gives Lustre	3.27	3.69	3.70	3.54	3.687	.029*
2	The Hair Oil Enhances Hair Growth	3.47	3.94	3.50	3.66	2.596	.081
3	The Hair Oil applying every day is good for hair	3.80	3.75	3.80	3.78	.019	.981
Cosmetics							
1	The Cosmetics remove Dark Spots	3.20	3.69	3.30	3.41	3.323	.041*

	and Blemishes						
2	The Cosmetics makes Skin Fairer and Younger	3.60	3.63	2.90	3.44	4.713	.012*
3	The Cosmetics Cause Allergies and Side effects	3.33	3.63	2.80	3.32	4.283	.017*
Detergent							
1	The Detergent Harm Your Hands	3.07	3.50	3.00	3.22	3.602	.032*
2	The Detergent gives shine to your clothes	3.53	3.75	3.30	3.56	2.187	.119
3	The Detergent Maintain the colour and Elegance of Clothes	3.53	3.69	3.30	3.54	1.569	.215

Source: Primary Data (Significant at 0.05 Level)

The F-test results relating to various factors have been rejected. Since their computed values is less than the 0.05 significance level regarding influencing factors where Bath soap and cosmetics factors, the factor regard to Shampoo Cleans Scalp and Hair Dandruff, the factor regard to Soap has Fragrance and gives good complexion/ colour of Skin, the factor regard to Hair Oil Gives Lustre, the factor regard to Detergent Harm Your Hands

The F-test results relating to several factors have been accepted since their computed value is more than the 0.05 significance level regarding influencing factors.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- Most of the women respondents belongs to the 20 – 40 years.
- Nearly 67% of respondents are Married women's.
- Majority of the respondents are House wife's (54%) and Private employees (32%).
- 62% of respondents belonged to the Nuclear Family.
- The family income of most of the respondents was less than Rs. 20,000.
- 44% of the respondents prefer Super Market to purchase FMCGs products.
- The respondents were influenced by the Advertisement to purchase from FMCG product.
- Majority (74%) of the respondents prefer Branded FMCG product.
- Most (37%) of the respondents brand preference of Himalaya Shampoo Brand.
- Majority (41%) of the respondents brand preference of Pears Both Soap Brand.
- Maximum number of the respondents brand preference of Colgate Tooth Paste Brand.
- Nearly 43% of the respondents brand preference is Parachute Hair Oil Brand.
- Most (32%) of the respondents brand preference of Lakme Cosmetics Brand.
- Majority (62%) of the respondents brand preference of Rin Detergent Washing Brand.

Suggestions

- Women are more concerned about price concessions, discounts, gifts, free home delivery, coupons and so on. The marketers must offer women the necessary promotional measures to buy fast moving consumer goods.
- The marketers need to identify who is taking and influencing women's purchasing decisions with respect to fast moving consumer goods. This will allow marketers to understand the influence of women, as different marketing campaigns can be targeted at each type of person. Marketing experts also examine the level of involvement of women and the number of brands available to determine and understand if they are involved in complex purchasing behaviors and usual buying behaviour.
- Companies with Indian brands, instead of following or waiting for the revolution, should take the leadership of the market through innovation in product improvement, sales technique and decision-making capacity to implement. The manager must use the policies implemented by the government for the consumer products sector from time to time.

CONCLUSIONS

The rapidly evolving market for consumer goods is becoming increasingly competitive. Therefore, fast-moving consumer goods manufacturers should understand a lot about consumers' interest in finding a higher sale of their products. The study of consumer behaviour is evolving rapidly as researchers recognize and implement new techniques to understand the nature of purchasing and consumption behaviours. Women play a vital role in purchasing behaviour and are more involved in purchasing activities. They are more attentive to prices, quality and faithful. Women tend to be more involved in shopping than men because they are traditionally family purchasing agents and perceive purchases as associated with their role in the family. Therefore, marketing experts should consider them of the utmost importance. and those who understand the behaviour of women consumers and plan their marketing strategies to meet the needs and aspirations of this target market will surely have an advantage over their competitors.

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